

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: ISRAEL

The Israel National Culture Collection of Algae (INCCA) for biodiversity conservation

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The Israel National Culture Collection of Algae (INCCA) was founded with the mission to preserve Israeli microalgae biodiversity and to establish not only a live culture collection, but also a resource of algae-related knowledge (Kaplan-Levy *et al.* 2020). Our aim is to document, isolate and preserve the microalgae and cyanobacteria biodiversity of the country for future scientific, industrial and educational purposes.

INCCA was established at the Kinneret Limnological Laboratory (KLL), Israel Oceanographic & Limnological Research (IOLR), located at the Sapir site (Tabgha), on the northwest shores of Lake Kinneret (Sea of Galilee), Israel. The culture collection at KLL-IOLR was initiated in the 1970s to provide cultures of phytoplankton species from Lake Kinneret for experimental work. In 2007 the [on-line phytoplankton catalogue of Lake Kinneret](#) was created with photos and descriptions of Lake species. Since 2012 many species were added to the culture collection as part of a project to DNA-barcode Lake Kinneret phytoplankton (Kaplan-Levy *et al.* 2016).

At present the collection contains 103 strains, mainly from the Cyanobacteria (39%), Chlorophyta (39%) and Charophyta (16%) divisions (Fig. 1). Each isolated culture was first identified by microscopy and later analysed by DNA barcoding. The DNA barcoding is done using a two-*loci* system, based on the amplification and sequencing of the *rbcL* gene and the *rRNA SSU-ITS* region.

The unialgal (xenic) cultures are maintained on agar plates or liquid medium, at constant illumination and temperature (20°C or 25°C). Since most isolates originate from Lake Kinneret they are accompanied by environmental data derived from over 50 years of [Lake Kinneret monitoring program](#), making INCCA unique among other culture collections. The advantage of such data is tremendous, since it enables linking environmental changes with the waxing and waning of microalgae species, as well as giving insights into allelopathic interactions. This knowledge on microalgae species can be tested in a lab and further exploited by industry.

The contribution of such a facility to a country is most significant, especially since the international supplementary agreement "The Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization (ABS)" entered into force in October 2014, under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). This agreement aims at sharing the benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources in a fair and equitable way. However, it complicates the translocation of microorganisms between countries, emphasizing the need for an accredited culture collection of algae to preserve a country's biodiversity, especially for species at risk of extinction. We therefore aspire to join the World Federation of Culture Collections (WFCC), and improve our hardware facilities to enable cryopreservation, and the expansion of the collection from

Fig. 1 Phylogenetic diversity of INCCA strains, March 2020, depicting the percentage of strains belonging to each phylum. Photographs of representatives from the Israel National Culture Collection are shown: Miozoa: (a) *Peridinium gatunense* INCCA-D1001. Chlorophyta: (b) *Mucidosphaerium pulchellum* INCCA-G1045; (c) *Ankyra* sp. INCCA-G1061; (d) *Lagerheimia citriformis* INCCA-G1047; (e) *Pediastrum duplex* INCCA-G1044. Cyanobacteria: (f) *Chrysochloris ovalisporum* INCCA-C3001; (g) *Pseudoanabaena* sp. INCCA-C2008; (h) *Limnococcus* sp. INCCA-1002; (i) *Chroococcus turgidus* INCCA-C1021. Charophyta: (j) *Mougeotia* sp. INCCA-Ch1006 (k) *Cosmarium* sp. INCCA-Ch1034.

diverse habitats to include micro-algae and cyanobacteria from all over Israel. In parallel, we aim to continue recording DNA-barcodes of isolates, as well as microscopic imagery to be added to the on-line phytoplankton catalogue.

By transforming INCCA into a formal internationally accredited collection that will expand to include species of microalgae from all types of habitats in Israel, we envision the first Middle-East facility for microalgal biodiversity preservation.

References

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